

COMPARISON OF TRICEPS SPLITTING VERSUS TRICEPS SPARING APPROACH IN EXTRA-ARTICULAR DISTAL HUMERUS FRACTURES

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the triceps-sparing VS triceps-splitting techniques in extra-articular distal humerus fractures in terms of mean range of motion (ROM) and mean disabilities of the arm, shoulder, and hand (DASH) Score.

Methods: A total of 124 patients who presented with isolated extra-articular distal humerus fractures were included in this randomized clinical trial (RCT). Patients were randomized into 2 groups; A and B, by generating random identity numbers using Microsoft excel for randomization. Group A underwent fixation using triceps-sparing approach while B patients operated using triceps-splitting approach. On the second day after surgery, the patient was discharged with detailed instructions for rehabilitation. The third follow-up took place three months after surgery, involving radiographic assessment of the elbow, measurement of the range of motion (ROM) using a goniometer, and evaluation with the Quick DASH score.

Results: The average age of the participants was 33.2 ± 7.5 years. In terms of gender distribution, 77 participants (62.1%) were male, while 47 participants (37.9%) were female. The Triceps Sparing Group averaged $139 \text{ degrees} \pm 5$, while the Triceps Split Group averaged $127 \pm 4 \text{ degrees}$ ($p\text{-value} < 0.0001$). Additionally, the DASH score revealed a notable difference in functional outcomes; the Triceps Sparing Group had a mean score of 6.9 ± 3.1 , compared to the Triceps Split Group's mean score of 11.8 ± 4.7 ($p\text{-value} < 0.0001$).

Conclusion: Both the triceps-splitting and triceps-sparing techniques are viable options for treating extra-articular distal humerus fractures. Nevertheless, the triceps sparing approach tends to result in a markedly improved range of motion and DASH scores compared to the splitting method.

INTRODUCTION

Distal humerus fractures (DHF) represent around 3% of all fractures in adults and nearly 16% of humeral fractures overall.¹ These injuries exhibit a bimodal age distribution: younger individuals often sustain them from high-energy impacts, whereas older adults are more likely to suffer from them due to low-energy falls

or accidents.² The main goal of treatment is to alleviate pain and restore the range of motion (ROM) in the elbow, aiming for a flexion arc between 30 to 130 degrees to support daily activities.³ Although non-surgical treatment was traditionally the preferred method for managing acute extra-articular DHFs,

there has been a notable shift towards surgical intervention. This change is largely attributed to the establishment of the AO fracture fixation principles, advancements in surgical techniques and implants, and a general improvement in patient outcomes.⁴ Surgical stabilization of extra-articular fractures of the distal humerus, specifically AO/OTA type A fractures, is often recommended due to its capacity to provide consistent alignment and potentially facilitate a faster recovery of arm function.⁵ These fractures can be managed through different surgical approaches, including those that involve splitting the triceps muscle or preserving it.⁶ The triceps-sparing method, as outlined by Schildhauer and colleagues, offers several benefits over the traditional triceps-splitting technique.⁷ Notably, it tends to produce less scar tissue, partly because it utilizes bloodless surgical planes and avoids damaging the triceps muscle directly. This can be advantageous in minimizing postoperative elbow stiffness. Furthermore, by sparing the triceps, the risk of nerve injury to the muscle is decreased, which may help preserve muscle strength and reduce the likelihood of postoperative weakness.⁸ Numerous studies have examined the functional outcomes for patients undergoing different surgical approaches [5]. The purpose of this study was to compare two techniques—the triceps-sparing and triceps-splitting methods—in treating extra-articular distal humerus fractures. The comparison focused on key recovery metrics, including range of motion (ROM) and the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand (DASH) score.

METHODS:

A total of 124 patients who presented with isolated extra-articular distal humerus fractures were included in this randomized clinical trial (RCT). Patients were recruited from the department of orthopedics, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot, from December 2024 to April 2024. Patients having AO type t3 A1-, AZ, and 43) aged 20 years and above, belonging to either gender, who presented within one week of sustaining an injury were included. While skeletally immature patients, concomitant fracture of the proximal humerus, those having neurological illness, degenerative arthritis of the elbow, or open fractures were excluded.

Patients were randomized into 2 groups; A and B, by generating random identity numbers using Microsoft excel for randomization. Group A underwent fixation using triceps-sparing approach while B patients operated using triceps-splitting approach. Post-operatively Radiographs were done to confirm adequacy of implant placement and fracture reduction, All patients were operated under general anaesthesia with the application of a tourniquet to the upper arm set at 100 mm Hg above the systolic blood pressure. They would be positioned lateral with their arms on a side post with their elbows flexed.

In the triceps-sparing surgical approach, an incision was carefully made along the midline, extending from the elbow to the tip of the olecranon. The surgeon gently separated the anterior-medial aspect of the triceps muscle from the medial intermuscular septum using a scalpel, carefully dissecting down to the bone. Once the muscle was elevated above the posterior edge of the intermuscular septum and the posterior humerus, a lateral window through the triceps was created. The radial nerve and profunda brachii artery were gently pushed into this window from behind the arm, allowing for safe lateral access. Sharp dissection was then performed between the lateral edge of the triceps muscle and the lateral intermuscular septum, down to the bone. This technique enabled the surgeon to address a humeral fracture while avoiding injury to critical neurovascular structures. The entire posterior surface of the humerus was then exposed by retracting the triceps muscle, taking care to protect the muscle and tendon integrity throughout.

The surgical approach involved splitting the triceps muscle by carefully separating the interval between its long and lateral heads. The medial head was then carefully sectioned longitudinally along its muscle fibers, which originate distal to the spiral groove and radial nerve. This incision was created distally through the olecranon, maintaining full-thickness fascial layers on both the medial and lateral sides. These fascial sleeves remained intact to ensure proper contact with the surrounding muscles: the flexor carpi ulnaris on the medial side and the anconeus on the lateral side. Following this exposure, the surgeon performed an open reduction of the distal humerus fracture, securing it with lag screws. The fixation was completed with either a single or dual columnar plate, based on the surgeon's judgment during the procedure.

On the second day after surgery, the patient was discharged with detailed instructions for rehabilitation. Follow-up appointments were scheduled to monitor for any potential complications. The first follow-up occurred two weeks post-operation, during which stitches were removed and X-rays of the elbow—both anteroposterior and lateral views—were taken to verify the correct placement of the implant. A second follow-up was conducted at five weeks, with additional radiographs of the elbow taken in the same views. The third follow-up took place three months after surgery, involving radiographic assessment of the elbow, measurement of the range of motion (ROM) using a goniometer, and evaluation with the Quick DASH score.

Data was analyzed using SPSS v23. An independent sample t-test was applied to compare the mean DASH score and ROM between the groups, taking p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

The baseline characteristics of the study participants were recorded and analyzed. The average age of the participants was 33.2 ± 7.5 years. The average body mass index (BMI) was measured at 25.6 kg/m^2 . In terms of gender distribution, 77 participants (62.1%) were male, while 47 participants (37.9%) were female. The majority of fractures reported were on the left side, accounting for 89 cases (71.8%), while 35 cases (28.2%) were on the right side (Table 1).

Regarding outcomes, the results showed a significant difference in range of motion (ROM) between the two groups. The Triceps Sparing Group averaged 139 degrees ± 5 , while the Triceps Split Group averaged 127 ± 4 degrees (p-value < 0.0001). Additionally, the DASH score revealed a notable difference in functional outcomes; the Triceps Sparing Group had a mean score of 6.9 ± 3.1 , compared to the Triceps Split Group's mean score of 11.8 ± 4.7 (p-value < 0.0001). These findings highlight the superior performance of the triceps sparing technique in both ROM and functional assessments (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age (Y)	33.2±7.5
BMI (Kg/m ²)	25.6±2.
Gender (%)	
Male	77 (62.1%)
Female	47 (37.9%)
Fracture Side (%)	
Left	89 (71.8%)
Right	35 (28.2%)

Table 2. Comparison of Study Outcomes.

	Triceps Sparing Group (N=62)	Triceps Split Group (N=62)	p-value
ROM (mean ± SD)	139±5	127±4	<0.0001
DASH (mean ± SD)	6.9±3.1	11.8±4.7	<0.0001

DISCUSSION:

This study aimed to evaluate and compare the clinical and functional outcomes of treating extra-articular distal humerus fractures using two different surgical

approaches: triceps splitting and triceps sparing techniques. The triceps sparing approach, originally detailed by Schildhauer, is actually an extension of the

bilaterotricipital method introduced by Alonso-Llames.⁹ Other approaches reported by various researchers involve detaching part of the extensor mechanism from the olecranon, which are classified as triceps reflecting techniques. In contrast, the true triceps sparing approach preserves the triceps insertion on the olecranon, minimizing muscle injury. This preservation is theorized to reduce postoperative complications such as elbow contracture.

Over time, many surgeons have adopted the triceps-sparing approach, tailoring their methods to various types of fractures. The bilaterotricipital incision was initially introduced by Alonso-Llames and later expanded by Schildhauer and colleagues to address distal extra-articular fractures.^{10,11} Research by Gerwin and others demonstrated that, with specific modifications, this technique can also be applied to fractures of the humerus shaft, whether located proximally or distally.¹² One advantage of this incision is that it eliminates the need to repair the extensor mechanism at the end of the procedure. It helps preserve the integrity of the triceps muscle, provides a clearer surgical field with reduced bleeding, and minimizes scar tissue formation. As a result, the postoperative strength of the triceps muscle is maintained, potentially preventing elbow contracture. However, this approach is technically demanding, as limited visibility of the triceps can make fracture reduction more difficult. Additionally, to enhance stability on the medial side, surgeons often need to isolate the ulnar nerve when placing plates, a step that is unnecessary with the triceps-split method.

Emmanuel et al. found significantly better elbow ROM in the triceps-sparing group as compared to the triceps-splining group (140.0+4.0 versus 126.0+10.0, $p < 0.001$).¹³ In another trial done by Zareztdeh et al. DASH score was compared between these two approaches, and it was shown that there was no statistically significant difference.¹⁴

Remia et al. directly compared a triceps-sparing approach to a triceps-splitting approach. They used the triceps spring approach described by Bryan and Morrey in nine of their patients with AO/OTA TYPE C distal humerus fractures and the triceps splitting approach in 6 patients with AO/OTA TYPE C distal

humerus fractures. They concluded that there was no difference in elbow ROM or triceps deficit.¹⁵

CONCLUSION:

Both the triceps-splitting and triceps-sparing techniques are viable options for treating extra-articular distal humerus fractures. Nevertheless, the triceps sparing approach tends to result in a markedly improved range of motion and DASH scores compared to the splitting method.

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